

REFORMING AND REGULATING THE DEPOSIT INSURANCE SYSTEM IN GEORGIA**David Tchiotashvili,***Doctor of Economics, Professor of Gori State University,
Corresponding Member of the Academy of Ecological Sciences of Georgia.*ORCID: 0000-0002-2500-6252**Khaliana Chitadze***Doctor of Economics, Assoc. Professor of Gori State University*ORCID: 0000-0001-6795-9484**Abstract**

The reform, regulation and further improvement of the deposit insurance system is an important proven mechanism for protecting depositors and, accordingly, the banking sector and maintaining the stability of the country's financial system. It allows for its effective management capabilities and ensures the protection of the financial market from various risks related to strengthening the financial security system of the state and the private sector, protecting depositors and preventing systemic crises in the banking sector.

The paper analyzes the further stages of the reform and regulation of deposit insurance in Georgia, its economic and financial impact and risk management mechanisms.

Keywords: 1. Deposit insurance; 2. Investment portfolio; 3. Financial stability; 4. System reform; 5. Risk management.

Introduction: The reform of the deposit insurance system in Georgia was carried out taking into account international principles, international practice, World Bank recommendations and the Association Agreement between Georgia and the European Union. For its effective functioning, it is important that the insurance margin is precisely defined and creates an appropriate guarantee of protection. The gradual increase in the insurance margin and its approximation to European standards is an important priority, and according to the basic principles of deposit insurance and best international practice, an increase in the margin is appropriate when the financial situation is sustainable and the banking sector is stable. In 2025, a combination of economic and financial progress was created, which created another prerequisite for the possibility of further increasing the insurance margin, so that the effect of the decision would be as painless as possible for commercial banks in terms of financial impact. Taking into account all of the above, starting from 2026, the size of the margin will be increased from 30,000 to 50,000 GEL. Further reform and regulation of the deposit insurance investment portfolio, its investment policy and management in Georgia can be achieved by developing a coherent and systematic strategy for the deposit insurance system.

Methodology: The paper covers the stages of further reform and regulation of the deposit insurance system portfolio in Georgia, risk management and its compliance with financial market requirements, and stages of development and regulation in Georgia.

Review: Deposit insurance and deposit insurance portfolio regulation in Georgia, which is based on the principles of safety, liquidity and diversification, has been introduced over the past eight years and continues to develop to this day. For the proper functioning of the deposit insurance system, it is important to correctly determine the insurance threshold and create an adequate guarantee of protection. According to the European Union standard, the insurance threshold is 100,000 euros, which is still an unrealistic indicator for

the reality of Georgia. In Georgia, the insurance threshold of the deposit insurance system at the first stage was 5,000 GEL for individuals, and at the second stage, starting in 2020, this threshold increased to 15,000 GEL. At the same stage, an important innovation was implemented with a view to the country's socio-economic development, and from 2022, insurance of legal entities was added to the system. This approach has led to even closer alignment with international practice, and the amount of insured deposits has increased by an average of 500 million GEL. In the third stage, starting in 2024, the deposit insurance limit has doubled to 30,000 GEL. Starting from April 1, 2026, in the fourth stage, the deposit insurance system is expanding again. The amount of the insured deposit of individuals and legal entities has increased from 30,000 GEL to 50,000 GEL. As of today, the amount of money available in all accounts of all depositors in commercial banks and micro banks is automatically insured without additional fees. This is the third time the limit has been increased.

The Deposit Insurance Supervisory Authority, guided by the international deposit insurance standards established by the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) and the core principles of the International Association of Deposit Insurance (IADI), ensures the reform of the investment policy of the deposit insurance risk portfolio, the functioning of a stable financial environment, the solution of the tasks facing the system and the promotion of its further development. It introduces the latest international and European trends in deposit insurance and formulates medium-term strategic plans taking into account the following main credit, liquidity, market, currency and operational risks.

As of today, the Georgian financial system is quite resilient and stable. In turn, the banking system is highly capitalized, liquid and profitable, which critically needs to protect financial security. As of 2025, a total of 19 members are involved in the deposit insurance system in Georgia, including 17 commercial banks (three of which are digital banks) and 2 micro

banks. The two largest of them, whose total assets account for more than 70% of the banking system, are listed on the London Stock Exchange. The banking system maintains a high level of capitalization, which contributes to the stability of the sector. The capital growth resource is positively assessed, both in terms of shareholder strength and profitability. The stability of the banking sector is also indicated by the loan portfolio, and it can be said that banks maintain an adequate level of liquid assets corresponding to the structure of liabilities.

Based on data for 2018-2025, the sharpest increase in insured deposits was recorded at the end of 2020, at 100.36%, which was associated with the increase in the insurance limit from 5,000 GEL to 15,000 GEL in

2020. The 29.88% increase in 2022 was due to the addition of legal entities. As of December 31, 2025, the volume of total deposits increased by 13.85% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year, of which deposits of individuals increased by 12.87%, and deposits of legal entities by 14.95%. For the same period, the total volume of insured deposits (individuals and legal entities) amounted to 12.25 billion GEL, of which 11.24 billion GEL were insured deposits of individuals, and 1.007 billion GEL were insured deposits of legal entities. In 2025, total insured deposits increased by 14.75% annually, insured deposits of individuals by 15.51%, and insured deposits of legal entities by 6.88%. For 2018-2025, the total volume and change of insured deposits of individuals and legal entities looks like this: Table N1

Table №1

Total volume of insured deposits of individuals and legal entities by year, (billion GEL) and change (%) 2018-2025.

Year	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Total Deposits	23.90	27.24	35.42	38.03	46.03	52.09	60,29	68.64
Change%		13.97	30.01	7.38	21.04	13.15	15.75	13.85
Deposits of Individuals	12.50	15.07	18.49	20.29	24.00	27.33	31.85	35.95
Change%		20.53	22.70	9.74	18.27	13.90	16.52	12.87
Deposits of Legal Entities	11.40	12.17	16.93	17.74	22.03	24.75	28.44	32.70
Change%		6.75	39.11	4.78	24.20	12.33	14.91	14.95
Total Insured Deposits	1.75	2.02	4.04	4.56	5.92	6.86	10.67	12.25
Change%		15.25	100.36	12.72	29.88	15.99	55.50	14.75

In 2025, 73,159,034 GEL was accumulated in the Deposit Insurance Fund as regular insurance contributions by commercial banks. Income received in the form of coupons and from funds placed on overnight deposits with the National Bank of Georgia amounted

to 26,752,054 GEL and 597,722 GEL, respectively. Income received from primary contributions amounted to 200,000 GEL, and other income amounted to 40,000 GEL. The income of the Deposit Insurance Fund in 2017-2025 looks like this: Table N2

Table №2

Income of the Deposit Insurance Fund in 2017-2025

Year	Initial contribution	Regular insurance contribution	Daily benefit	Coupon	Other income	Total income
2017	1,600,000	0	0	0	0	1,600,000
2018	0	13,843,674	0	349,391	0	14,193,065
2019	0	16,787,385	0	1,541,832	0	18,329,218
2020	0	22,687,212	0	3,436,201	0	26,123,412
2021	0	30,674,444	0	5,229,436	0	35,903,880
2022	100,000	37,678,392	561,955	8,477,992	0	46,818,339
2023	100,000	42,393,708	1,543,994	13,101,777	0	57,139,479
2024	100,000	64,264,041	713,936	19,651,700	26.317	84,755,955
2025	200,000	73,159,034	597,722	26,752,054	40,000	100,748,810
Total	2,100,000	301,487,889	3,417,608	78,540,383	66.317	385,612,197

As of December 2025, 97% of depositors are fully insured, while 89% of legal entities are fully insured. 57% of insured deposits of individuals are insured in national currency, and 43% in foreign currency. In the case of insured deposits of legal entities, 78% of insured deposits are insured in national currency, and 22% in foreign currency. In terms of total insured deposits, these figures are 59% and 41%, respectively.

Currently, in order to maintain the security and liquidity of the Deposit Insurance Fund, funds are invested only in low-risk assets, treasury securities. The

agency also places free funds in an overnight deposit account at the National Bank of Georgia, where the annual interest rate is determined by the monetary policy rate.

Conclusion: Deposit and depositor insurance is one of the most important components and a continuously developing strategic process, on which the stability of the banking sector and the effective functioning of other financial institutions significantly depend, which can be achieved by developing a consistent and systematic strategy for the deposit insurance system

and its further reform, taking into account the basic principles of the International Deposit Insurance Association and the requirements set out in European directives.

References

1. Deposit Insurance Agency of Georgia www.diagency.ge
2. International Association of Deposit Insurers (IADI)
3. Bank for International Settlements <https://www.bis.org/index.htm>
4. Ministry of finance of Georgia www.mof.gov.ge
5. National Bank of Georgia www.nbg.gov.ge
6. Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development of Georgia www.economy.gov.ge
7. World Bank for European Reconstruction and Development. www.eeas.europa.eu
8. National Statistics Office of Georgia. www.geostat.ge